

Impact of atmospheric boundary layer profiling: Urban environments

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1 Introduction

The Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) over urban areas depicts a crucial zone of interaction between the synoptic-scale weather and direct surface-driven impacts on the atmosphere. The added heat and surface roughness, as well as the release of pollutants and reduction in moisture sources mean the urban boundary layer (UBL) is characterised by specific climate and flow conditions.

With the majority of the global population living in urban areas, they are increasingly moving into the focus of climate change adaptation. For example, global initiatives like *The Covenant of Mayors* are seeking solutions to make cities more resilient through adaptation measures. To make an appropriate roadmap to implement this planning should be based on data collection, modelling and simulations. Decision-makers usually have a wide range of tools at their disposal to address these challenges and develop resilience, but a better understanding of the microclimate and the environment of the settlement, as well the circumstances and sequences of extreme weather events could be essential to make informed decisions and choose proper development paths. The development of Urban Heat Islands or the propagation of air pollutants requires targeted measures. An improved understanding of processes in the UBL is critical for the evaluation of high-resolution numerical weather prediction and air quality assessment in cities, but also to inform sustainable urban planning and efficient disaster risk management (e.g. heat risk mitigation and adaptation).

In this chapter, we highlight a few examples of novel ground-based remote sensing profile data and products that showcase the importance of detailed ABL information for near-surface atmospheric conditions in urban settings. To ensure such data can be exploited effectively by municipalities, urban planners, or operational agencies, e.g. responsible for the monitoring and forecasting of air quality or microclimates, the information may need to be provided in targeted formats. Discussions are ongoing between different actors to develop the required communication strategies and to ensure applied products are made available that can be transformed into applicable decision support tools.

2 Low-level jet

Contribution: Jonathan Céspedes

Both the Low-Level Jet (LLJ) and the Urban Heat Island (UHI) are common nocturnal phenomena. While the canopy layer UHI has been studied extensively, interactions of the LLJ and the urban atmosphere in general (and the UHI in particular) have received less attention. In the framework of the PANAME initiative in the Paris region, continuous profiles of wind speed and vertical velocity were recorded with two Doppler Wind Lidars (DWL) - for the first time allowing for a detailed investigation of the summertime LLJ characteristics in the region. Jets are detected for 70% of the examined nights, often simultaneously at an urban and a suburban site highlighting the LLJ regional spatial extent. Emerging at around sunset, the mean LLJ duration is ~10 h, the mean wind speed is ~9ms⁻¹, and the average core height is 400 m above the city. Many events show signatures in the temporal evolution that indicate that the inertial oscillation mechanism plays a role in the jet development: a clockwise veering of the wind direction and a rapid acceleration followed by a slower deceleration. The horizontal wind shear below the LLJ core induces variance in the vertical velocity (σ_w^2) above the urban canopy layer. It is shown that σ_w^2 is a powerful predictor for regional contrast in air temperature, as the UHI intensity decreases exponentially with increasing σ_w^2 and strong UHI values only occur when σ_w^2 is very weak. This study demonstrates how DWL observations in cities provide valuable insights into near-surface processes relevant to human and environmental health.

Figure 1. Mean profiles of a) horizontal wind speed and b) median profiles of vertical velocity variance σ_w^2 . The solid lines represent the composite profile with all 30-min profiles detected as LLJ, and the shadows denote $1\pm\text{std}$. Each panel presents the respective profiles for each σ_w^2 class: red is low σ_w^2 , orange is moderate and blue is strong σ_w^2 . Céspedes et al (2024) - ACP <https://doi.org/10.5194/equsphere-2024-520>

Figure 2. Relations between the nocturnal average of ΔUHI intensity for all cloud-free nights in the study period and a) 10 m agl wind speed at Montsouris park, an urban reference site. The dots are coloured by surface wind direction at Montsouris. The dashed black curve is the best fit for the data: $y = 4((x-1.1)^{-0.8})$, and it follows the empirical relationship described by Oke (1973) b) the σ_w^2 at 238 m agl, dots are coloured by the LLJ core height above the ground surface. The dashed black curve represents the best non-linear fit found for the data collected in the Paris region, with ΔUHI calculated using QUALAIR-SU data. The dotted black curve represents the same but using data collected by a surface-based station installed at Boulevard de Capucines for a shorter time period. Both curves represent the equation: $y = -1.39 \log(x) + 0.84$. The background shading indicates the LLJ classes. In all subplots, dots and triangles represent nights with and without LLJ events, respectively. Céspedes et al. (2024) - ACP <https://doi.org/10.5194/equsphere-2024-520>

3 Wind profile monitoring for wind tunnel applications

Contribution: Klára Jurčáková, Radka Kellnerová, Jonnathan Cespedes
For more details see Céspedes VMG (not yet online)

To study the dispersion of pollutants in urban areas and to evaluate potential regulatory measures, both numerical and physical modelling tools at street scales are essential tools. The pollution dispersion in the complex urban canopy layer is challenging to predict because of the high level of turbulence in the driving wind field. To inform model setup and to assess simulation results, real-world profile observations are urgently needed. While a representative climatology of the mean wind profile is very valuable, also turbulence statistics such as variance in all three wind components, integral length scales, and spectral composition are required.

Physical modelling is based on the analogy between the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) and the aerodynamic boundary layer above a flat surface. The flow properties of a real site and its model are analogous if the ratios of all acting forces are identical. These ratios are called similarity numbers, e.g., Reynolds or Richardson numbers. Investigation of scaled atmospheric flows in laboratory conditions is advantageous since the conditions during measurements are under control, repeatable, and statistically stationary. Moreover, precise state-of-the-art experimental techniques (e.g. Laser Doppler Anemometry, Particle Image Velocimetry, Thermal Anemometry, and Flame Ionisation Detector with fast temporal response) can be employed at ease.

The wind engineering community sees the ABL as a special case of an aerodynamic boundary layer. To apply theoretical assumptions, certain criteria need to be fulfilled, such as a logarithmic vertical profile of the mean wind speed, a fully developed turbulence spectra with clearly pronounced inertial subrange, and temporal stationarity. However, such characteristics are very seldom present in real-world atmospheric measurements. The ABL measurements are very often subjected to spatial variations in surface roughness (inhomogeneous terrain) and a nonstationary forcing (changes in the synoptic flow and changes in the turbulent surface heat fluxes). Hence they do not fit into aerodynamicists' expectations.

Given real-world data for specific atmospheric conditions are rare, especially for specific sites of interest, best practice guidelines and tables with recommended values for the key parameters were developed, such as the frequently applied ESDU (originally the 'Engineering Sciences Data Unit') published in 2002 in UK and VDI 3783 Blatt 12 from The Association of German Engineers originally published in 2000 with the major revision in 2022. Both guidance documents provide reference values for wind profiles in the atmospheric boundary layers as a function of surface roughness classes - from desert and ice flat plains to the city centres. Tabled values consist of parameters that describe the logarithmic vertical profile of horizontal wind speed (roughness length, zero-plane displacement height), vertical profiles of turbulence intensity for each wind component, the spectral distribution of the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) and the vertical profile of the integral length scales. Other very old references used in both guidelines in the work of J. Counihan (1975). They collected a wide range of ABL tower measurements from years 1880 to 1972 and summarised them in the graphs and tables giving typical values of the aerodynamic parameters as the power-law exponent, roughness length, integral length scales, and power spectra.

Experimental equipment has undergone a fundamental enhancement since then. Stationary time series of all three wind velocity components are needed at high temporal frequency to estimate all turbulence properties reliably, as they are calculated from the time series of the fluctuations around a stationary mean value. Any biases or temporal trends can affect the accuracy of the mean and may hence alter the resulting turbulence estimates. Therefore, it is essential to choose appropriate averaging periods. The classical wind-speed spectrum from Van der Hoven (1957) shows that the dominant temporal scales of turbulence have a duration of about 1 to 5 minutes, and the dominant synoptic variations have a frequency of several days. These two spectral peaks are separated by "the spectral gap" at approximately 30 to 60 minutes which conveniently separates synoptic and turbulent motions. Turbulence estimations from classical Eddy Covariance systems hence often work with an averaging period of 30-60 min. To account for variations in atmospheric stability, the optimal averaging period can be chosen inversely proportional to the mean wind speed from the

aerodynamic point of view. Note that the significance of the spectral gap has been questioned lately (Larsen et al., 2016).

Traditionally, such information is derived from tall tower observations. The advantage of the mast measurements is a high sampling frequency of data acquisition; however, towers are usually insufficiently high and their deployment in urban settings is very rare as it is generally difficult to find a suitable location and they are expensive to build. Remote sensing profilers can be used to monitor the atmospheric boundary layer continuously. Wind climatology data at a site of interest would provide more accurate initial data for the microscale modellers (both the wind-tunnel and numerical simulations). Doppler wind lidars are powerful systems to obtain long-term observations of all three wind components at high temporal resolution along a vertical profile. The first available measurement level, the range of the observations in the vertical and also the vertical resolution differ between instrument models and measurement setups (see [Preissler et al. 2024](#)).

4 Urban boundary layer dynamics

Contribution: Simone Kotthaus, Martial Haeffelin, Pauline Martinet

The spatial distribution of heat, moisture and atmospheric pollutants is of course largely affected by heterogeneity of the respective sources, but also transport mechanisms in the atmospheric boundary layer play an important role. To better understand the relative importance of mixing, dilution, entrainment and advection in the urban atmosphere, it is vital to quantify the effectiveness of vertical motions in the atmosphere, i.e. the atmospheric stability. It is known that the added heat and surface roughness over cities enhance thermal buoyancy and momentum transport, thereby destabilising the near-surface atmosphere. While stable stratification over rural surfaces is the norm at night, the boundary layer over dense urban surfaces is more likely to remain neutral or even slightly unstable even at night. During the day, the height of the convective boundary layer can be greater due to the stronger vertical motion (see Figure 3). However, to date, continuous monitoring of these effects is rare and multiple variables need to be observed simultaneously to be able to quantify the thermal stratification of the atmosphere on the one hand and the horizontal and vertical motion on the other. Turbulence observations can provide added value as they can be interpreted as a direct assessment of mixing processes.

Figure 3: Seasonal diurnal pattern of mixed layer height (MLH) relative to time since sunrise detected at a central urban and a sub-urban location in the megacity of Paris, France, during the period Dec 2016 – Oct 2019. (top row) solid line is the median MLH with shading the inter-quartile range, (middle row) median and inter-quartile range of instantaneous differences, and (bottom row) number of samples. Cimini et al. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42865-020-00003-8>

In the context of the PANAME (<https://paname.aeris-data.fr/>) initiative in the Paris region (France), effective project collaborations enabled the design of a detailed ground-based remote sensing monitoring network. Three supersites were installed along a suburban-urban transect, each equipped with microwave radiometers (MWR) to monitor temperature profiles (see also <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11237313>), Doppler wind lidars to record vertical profiles of wind and turbulence, as well as automatic lidars and ceilometers (ALC) that track aerosol backscatter and cloud base height. On-going analyses of these multi-variate network data highlights the capabilities of detailed instrumental synergy (see also Burgos et al, [10.5281/zenodo.10986522](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10986522)) to better understand the link between synoptic flow and surface-driven processes in the urban environment (e.g. Kotthaus et al., 2024).

5 Urban air quality

Contribution: Henri Diémoz, Francesca Barnaba, Annachiara Bellini

Aerosol regional transport impact on AQ: examples of the Po Valley

The operational use of active remote sensing from ALC systems has been a key tool to reveal and quantify the export of pollutants from the Po Valley to surrounding areas. A recent study performed using data collected in the northwestern Italian Alps showed that, mostly due to thermal winds producing typical mountain-valley daily circulations, Po Valley pollution markedly affects PM-related AQ in the surrounding ‘pristine’ mountain environments, namely the Alpine and pre-Alpine areas (Diémoz et al., 2019a,b). The phenomenon was first observed by lidar observations performed at the EC-JRC in Ispra (VA), about 60 km northwest of the Milan metropolitan area (Barnaba et al., 2010), and has been recently thoroughly investigated by means of continuous (24/7) data from the ALICENet ALC systems at Milan and Aosta, respectively within and at the NW border of the Po Valley (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Locations of the two ALICENet ALC systems at Aosta and Milan in the Po Valley, Italy.

The local EPA (Arpa Valle d’Aosta) is operating an ALC at Aosta to complement standard AQMN measurements. Since its first deployment, this system captures recurrent aerosol layers arriving in the afternoon and persisting during the night, characterising the aerosol vertical profiles up to 4 km altitude. It has been demonstrated (Diémoz et al., 2019a,b) that this is a regional phenomenon mostly driven by mountain-valley breezes bringing polluted aerosol plumes from the Po Valley to the surrounding mountainous regions (Aosta, Figure 5a). Simultaneous ALC observations performed at the Po Valley pollution hotspot of Milan show how this phenomenon produces the reverse effect in the centre of the valley, i.e., a removal or ‘cleaning’ of PM in the afternoon hours (Figure 5b).

(a) ALICENet lev2 profiles in Aosta

(b) ALICENet lev2 profiles in Milan

Figure 5: Continuous aerosol profiles (aerosol scattering ratio, ALICENet Level 2 profiles) from ALC at Aosta and Milan in the period 25-31 August 2015. Adapted from Diemoz et al. 2019a.

Overall, the operational use of ALC systems with support of modelling tools and in-situ AQ observations revealed a major impact of such a regular, ‘aerosol tide’ on the trans-regional AQ. Based on 3 years of continuous measurements it was shown that in relatively ‘clean’ environments such as the Aosta Alpine area, this regular import from the Po Valley leads to a significant increase of PM10 concentrations (up-to a factor of 3.5). These aerosol-rich layers can extend to a depth of up to 4 km and are observed with a frequency of 50% of the days overall, but occur with a frequency of up to 93% when only days with easterly winds (i.e., outflow from the Po Basin) are considered and 100% if air mass residence time over the Po Valley is > 10 h (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Contingency table based on 3-years (2015-2017) of continuous data showing occurrences of detection of the aerosol layer by the ALC in relation to a) wind direction and b) residence time of air masses in the Po Valley (evaluated by 48 h back-trajectories). The orange (blue) boxes represent cases when the aerosol layer is (is not) present. Adapted from Diemoz et al. 2019b.

Coupling of ALC observations with Positive Matrix Factorisation (PMF) of chemical properties at surface level revealed that particles advected from the Po Valley to the northwestern Alps are mostly of secondary origin and mainly composed of nitrates, sulphates, and ammonium. An important organic component was also detected in the warm season (Diemoz et al., 2019b).

The operational deployment of ALC remote sensing systems also allows better understanding and interpretation of particular long and short range transport phenomena impacting PM-related AQ, including (but not limited to) desert dust or fire plumes. An example of this capability is provided below (Figure 7): a particular case of rapid and intense deterioration of AQ in the urban area of Milan in April 2020. The episode was due to an extended (about 100 km) gust front originating from the cold and intense Bora wind from East (Figure 7), raising and transporting farming residuals across the entire Po Valley. In fact, the episode was preceded by a particularly dry period, an anomalous condition affecting most of Europe in that month. Note that a quite similar event was recorded at the same sites also in April 2022.

Figure 7: a) Central Milan camera showing the rapid decrease of visibility/increase of PM on 14/07/2020 (from top to bottom: pictures at 16:08, 16:15, 16:20, 16:25 UTC), b) Po Valley satellite true colour image, and c) 10 m wind speed and direction simulated by WRF over North Italy (14/07/2020 17:00 UTC, courtesy of Stefano Federico CNR/ISAC) illustrating the extension of the gust and wind fronts generating this effect.

The corresponding aerosol mass concentration profiles derived from ALC observations at Milan (Figure 8a) nicely capture the timing of the plume arrival and show the vertical extent of the

particle-rich layer associated with the episode. The plume continued to travel westward and was detected by the ALC at Aosta (Figure 8b) four hours later, indicating a horizontal wind speed of more than 12 m/s.

Figure 8: ALICenet aerosol mass profiles in a) Milan and b) Aosta, 14 April 2020.

6 References

- Adam, M., Nicolae, D., Stachlewska, I. S., Papayannis, A., and Balis, D.: Biomass burning events measured by lidars in EARLINET – Part 1: Data analysis methodology, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 20, 13905–13927, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-20-13905-2020>, 2020.
- Biniotoglou, I.; Giuseppe, D.; Baars, H.; Belegante, L.; Marinou, E. A methodology for cloud masking uncalibrated lidar signals. In *EPJ Web of Conferences 2018*, 176, 05048; EDP Sciences
- Brocard, E., Philipona, R., Haeefe, A., Romanens, G., Mueller, A., Ruffieux, D., Simeonov, V., and Calpini, B.: Raman Lidar for Meteorological Observations, RALMO – Part 2: Validation of water vapor measurements, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 6, 1347–1358, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-6-1347-2013>, 2013.
- Céspedes, J., Kotthaus, S., Preissler, J., Toupoint, C., Thobois, L., Drouin, M.-A., Dupont, J.-C., Fauchoux, A., and Haeffelin, M.: The Paris Low-Level Jet During PANAME 2022 and its Impact on the Summertime Urban Heat Island, *EGUsphere* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2024-520>, 2024.
- Cimini, D., Hocking, J., De Angelis, F., Cersosimo, A., Di Paola, F., Gallucci, D., Gentile, S., Gerdali, E., Larosa, S., Nilo, S., Romano, F., Ricciardelli, E., Ripepi, E., Viggiano, M., Luini, L., Riva, C., Marzano, F. S., Martinet, P., Song, Y. Y., Ahn, M. H., and Rosenkranz, P. W.: RTTOV-gb v1.0 – updates on sensors, absorption models, uncertainty, and availability, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 12, 1833–1845, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-1833-2019>, 2019.

De Angelis, F., Cimini, D., Hocking, J., Martinet, P., and Kneifel, S.: RTTOV-gb – adapting the fast radiative transfer model RTTOV for the assimilation of ground-based microwave radiometer observations, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 9, 2721–2739, doi:10.5194/gmd-9-2721-2016, Online: <http://www.geosci-model-dev.net/9/2721/2016/>, 2016.

ESDU (1985): Characteristics of atmospheric turbulence near the ground. Part II: single point data for strong winds (neutral atmosphere) in ESDU 85020 International

Leuenberger, D., Haeefe, A., Omanovic, N., Fengler, M., Martucci, G., Calpini, B., Fuhrer, O., & Rossa, A. (2020). Improving High-Impact Numerical Weather Prediction with Lidar and Drone Observations, *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 101(7), E1036-E1051

Dinoev, T., Simeonov, V., Arshinov, Y., Bobrovnikov, S., Ristori, P., Calpini, B., Parlange, M., and van den Bergh, H.: Raman Lidar for Meteorological Observations, RALMO – Part 1: Instrument description, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 6, 1329–1346, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-6-1329-2013>, 2013.

Dione, C., Haeffelin, M., Burnet, F., Lac, C., Canut, G., Delanoë, J., Dupont, J.-C., Jorquera, S., Martinet, P., Ribaud, J.-F., and Toledo, F.: Role of thermodynamic and turbulence processes on the fog life cycle during SOFOG3D experiment, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 23, 15711–15731, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-23-15711-2023>, 2023.

Gultepe, I., Pearson, G., Milbrandt, J. A., Hansen, B., Platnick, S., Taylor, P., Gordon, M., Oakley, J. P., and Cober, S. G.: The Fog Remote Sensing and Modelling Field Project, *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, 90, 341–360, <https://doi.org/10.1175/2008BAMS2354.1>, 2009

Kotthaus, S., Haeffelin, M., Céspedes, J., Ribaud, J.-F., Dupont, J.-C., Drouin, M.-A., Martinet, P., and Lemonsu, A.: Linking synoptic flow and city dynamics: PANAME observations of the Paris urban boundary layer, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-18040, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-18040>, 2024

Martucci, G., Navas-Guzmán, F., Renaud, L., Romanens, G., Gamage, S. M., Hervo, M., Jeannet, P., and Haeefe, A.: Validation of pure rotational Raman temperature data from the Raman Lidar for Meteorological Observations (RALMO) at Payerne, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 14, 1333–1353, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-14-1333-2021>, 2021.

Lange, D., Behrendt, A., & Wulfmeyer, V. (2019). Compact operational tropospheric water vapor and temperature Raman lidar with turbulence resolution. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 46, 14844– 14853. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GL085774>

Laitinen A., 2019, Utilization of drones in vertical profile measurements of the atmosphere, Master of science thesis, University of Tampere, <https://trepo.tuni.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/116237/LaitinenAntti.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y>

Newsom, R.K.; Turner, D.D.; Lehtinen, R.; Münkel, C.; Kallio, J.; Roininen, R. Evaluation of a compact broadband differential absorption lidar for routine water vapor profiling in the atmospheric boundary layer. *J. Atmos. Ocean. Technol.* 2020, 37, 47–65.

Nicolae, D., Vasilescu, J., Talianu, C., Binietoglou, I., Nicolae, V., Andrei, S., and Antonescu, B.: A neural network aerosol-typing algorithm based on lidar data, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 18, 14511–14537, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-18-14511-2018>, 2018.

Osborne, M., Malavelle, F. F., Adam, M., Buxmann, J., Sugier, J., Marengo, F., and Haywood, J.: Saharan dust and biomass burning aerosols during ex-hurricane Ophelia: observations from the new UK lidar and sun-photometer network, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 19, 3557–3578, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-19-3557-2019>, 2019.

Preissler, J., O'Connor, E., Kayser, M., Hervo, M., Lehmann, V., Toupoint, C., Holst, C. C., Gryning, S.-E., Batchvarova, E., Céspedes, J., & Bertolasco, E. (2024). JND European networks observing the atmospheric boundary layer: Overview, access and impacts Chapter: Doppler lidar (DL). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11561263>

Ribaud, J.-F., Haeffelin, M., Dupont, J.-C., Drouin, M.-A., Toledo, F., and Kotthaus, S.: PARAFOG v2.0: a near-real-time decision tool to support nowcasting fog formation events at local scales, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 14, 7893–7907, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-14-7893-2021>, 2021.

Rüfenacht, R., Haefele, A., Pospichal, B., Cimini, D., Bircher-Adrot, S., Turp, M., Sugier, J. EUMETNET opens to microwave radiometers for operational thermodynamical profiling in Europe. *Bull. of Atmos. Sci. & Technol.* 2, 4, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42865-021-00033-w>, 2021.

Salamanca, Francisco & Georgescu, Matei & Mahalov, Alex & Moustou, M. & Martilli, Alberto. (2016). Citywide Impacts of Cool Roof and Rooftop Solar Photovoltaic Deployment on Near-Surface Air Temperature and Cooling Energy Demand. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*. 161. 10.1007/s10546-016-0160-y.

Toledo, F., Haeffelin, M., Wærsted, E., and Dupont, J.-C.: A new conceptual model for adiabatic fog, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 21, 13099–13117, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-21-13099-2021>, 2021.

Toporov, M., and U. Löhnert, 2020: Synergy of Satellite- and Ground-Based Observations for Continuous Monitoring of Atmospheric Stability, Liquid Water Path and Integrated Water Vapor, *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 59(7), 1153-1170, <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAMC-D-19-0169.1>

VDI 3783 Blatt 12 (2022): Environmental Meteorology—Physical Modelling of Flow and Dispersion Processes in the Atmospheric Boundary Layer—Application of Wind Tunnels. Beuth Verlag: Düsseldorf, Germany, 2000.

Weckwerth, T. M., Weber, K. J., Turner, D. D., & Spuler, S. M. (2016). Validation of a Water Vapor Micropulse Differential Absorption Lidar (DIAL), *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 33(11), 2353-2372.